

Statistical analysis plan: Emulation of EMPA-REG using the NDA

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1. Target Trial Emulation

Randomised trials are the gold standard for evaluating the effectiveness and safety of interventions due to their ability to minimise bias through randomisation. However, these trials can be prohibitively expensive, unethical, or time-consuming, making them impractical in certain scenarios. In such cases, observational data can serve as an alternative to answer similar research questions[1].

The design of observational studies is critical; incorrect choices, such as improper specification of the start of follow-up, can introduce self-inflicted biases. Ensuring the validity of findings from observational data requires meticulous attention to study design and analytical methods to mitigate these biases. Despite these challenges, when executed properly, observational studies can provide important insights into the effectiveness of interventions, especially in situations where randomised trials are not feasible[2].

Explicitly defining the protocol of the target trial before emulating it using observational data is crucial for avoiding common design pitfalls. For instance, observational studies that include prevalent users of a treatment are prone to selection bias. This type of bias occurs when participants who had already started the treatment before the follow-up period are included in the active arm of the study. These participants must have survived and remained event-free (assuming no history of the outcome event is part of the eligibility criteria) while receiving treatment up until the follow-up begins. Consequently, those who initiate treatment and survive this arbitrary period tend to be artificially healthy, leading to biased results[3].

1.1 Designing a target trial

The first step in using observational data to emulate a randomised trial is to specify the protocol of the ideal trial that would have been conducted, considering the constraints of the available data. This involves defining several key elements: eligibility criteria for participants, the treatment strategies to be compared, the procedures for assigning these treatments, the outcomes to be measured, the duration and methods of follow-up, the causal contrasts of interest, and the statistical analysis plan. In this context, the target trial must be designed as a pragmatic trial, which is more flexible and reflective of real-world conditions than a placebo-controlled trial. This is because observational data inherently lack the controlled environment of a placebo group[4].

1.2 Components of target trial protocol

Successful emulation of a target trial requires a proper definition of **time zero** of follow-up in the observational data, also referred to as baseline. **Eligibility criteria** need to be met at that point but not later; study outcomes begin to be counted after that point but not earlier.[5]

In our target trial, the natural start of follow-up will be the time when the **treatment strategy** is assigned, which often occurs either shortly before or at the same time as initiation of the treatment strategy. **Follow-up** should start when eligibility criteria are met, treatment strategies are assigned, and outcomes begin to be counted. Follow-up continues until the earliest occurrence of an outcome, censoring, death, competing events, or end of follow-up.

Causal parameter of Interest:

The primary causal contrasts in randomised trials are often the intention-to-treat (ITT) effect and the per-protocol effect. The ITT effect compares treatment strategies assigned at baseline regardless of

subsequent adherence, while the per-protocol effect assesses the effect of fully adhering to the assigned treatment strategies. Both effects are valuable and can be estimated in observational studies if appropriate data and methodologies are available.

Intention-to-Treat Analysis

In randomised trials, the ITT effect is straightforward to estimate, as treatment assignment is random and adherence is not considered. However, emulating this in observational studies is challenging. One approach is to use prescription data to designate treatment assignment for the entire follow-up period based on the first prescription. Another strategy is to compare treatment initiators, considering patients "treated" or "untreated" based on the first treatment initiated, regardless of long-term adherence. Both approaches require adjustments for baseline confounding to balance patient characteristics between treatment groups. [6]

Per-Protocol Analysis

The per-protocol approach, in contrast, accounts for nonadherence by evaluating the comparative effectiveness of treatments that patients adhered to within randomised groups. This approach is particularly useful in noninferiority trials or when assessing treatment safety. Estimating the per-protocol effect requires adjustments for both baseline and postbaseline confounding, as postbaseline prognostic factors can influence adherence and be affected by prior adherence.[3, 7]

In emulating this target trial using NDA data, we will define the treatment strategy as **"taking active/comparator therapy continuously during the follow-up, unless otherwise clinically indicated."** To estimate the per-protocol effect, we will consider three essential points:[7]

- Non-Censoring for Clinical Discontinuation: Data from participants who stop treatment for clinical reasons, such as side effects, should not be censored as they are not deviating from the protocol.
- Censoring for Uncertain Treatment: Data should be censored when it is no longer certain that participants are receiving the treatment.
- Adjustment for Incomplete Adherence: Adjustments must be made for confounding due to incomplete adherence.

Methodological Considerations

For ITT analysis, standard methods are used to adjust for baseline covariates. In per-protocol analysis, participants deviating from the treatment strategy are censored, and advanced methods such as g-methods [8], or Targeted maximum likelihood [9] are used to adjust for prognostic factors associated with adherence. Emulating a per-protocol design in an observational study mirrors a randomised controlled trial (RCT) but requires special consideration for time zero and additional adjustments for confounding at both baseline and follow-up stages. This comprehensive approach ensures that the analysis accurately reflects the real-world application of treatment strategies and provides reliable estimates of their effects.

2. Overview of [EMPA-REG](#) trial

The EMPA-REG OUTCOME trial was a pivotal clinical study aimed at evaluating the cardiovascular effects of empagliflozin, a sodium-glucose co-transporter 2 (SGLT2) inhibitor, in patients with type 2 diabetes and established cardiovascular disease. The primary goal was to assess whether empagliflozin could reduce the incidence of major adverse cardiovascular events, defined as cardiovascular death, non-fatal myocardial infarction, or non-fatal stroke. This extensive, multi-centre, randomised, double-

blind, placebo-controlled trial enrolled over 7,000 participants, who were followed for a median of 3.1 years.

The results of the EMPA-REG OUTCOME trial were ground-breaking, demonstrating a 38% relative reduction in cardiovascular death, a 35% relative reduction in hospitalisation for heart failure, and 32% relative reduction in all-cause mortality among those treated with empagliflozin compared to placebo. These findings marked a significant advancement in the treatment of type 2 diabetes, as it was the first time a glucose lowering medication was shown to have substantial cardiovascular benefits. The trial also observed that empagliflozin led to modest reductions in blood glucose levels and body weight, alongside a slight increase in LDL cholesterol. Overall, the EMPA-REG OUTCOME trial established empagliflozin not only as an effective glucose-lowering agent but also as a crucial therapeutic option for reducing cardiovascular risk in people with diabetes[10].

Study design:

EMPA-REG OUTCOME was a randomised, double-blind, placebo-controlled trial to assess the effect of once-daily empagliflozin (at a dose of either 10 mg or 25 mg) versus placebo on cardiovascular events in adults with type 2 diabetes at high cardiovascular risk against a background of standard care. Patients were treated at 590 sites in 42 countries. The trial continued until an adjudicated primary outcome event had occurred in at least 691 patients [11].

The trial included adults (aged 18 years and over) with type 2 diabetes with a body-mass index of 45 or less and an estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR) of at least 30 ml per minute per 1.73 m² of body-surface area. All the patients had established cardiovascular disease and had received no glucose-lowering agents for at least 12 weeks before randomisation and had a glycated haemoglobin level of at least 7.0% and no more than 9.0% or had received stable glucose-lowering therapy for at least 12 weeks before randomization and had a glycated haemoglobin level of at least 7.0% and no more than 10.0%. Exclusion criteria included significant renal impairment, recent history of acute coronary or cerebrovascular events and heart failure requiring hospitalisation.

Outcome:

The primary outcome was a composite of death from cardiovascular causes, nonfatal myocardial infarction (excluding silent myocardial infarction), or nonfatal stroke. The key secondary outcome was a composite of the primary outcome plus hospitalisation for unstable angina.

Statistical analysis:

The statistical analysis of the EMPA-REG OUTCOME trial primarily aimed to test the noninferiority of empagliflozin compared to placebo for reducing major adverse cardiovascular events, with a hazard ratio margin of 1.3. A four-step hierarchical testing strategy was employed: noninferiority for the primary outcome, noninferiority for the key secondary outcome, superiority for the primary outcome, and superiority for the key secondary outcome. Interim data were included in a new-drug application to the FDA, and the Haybittle-Peto rule was used, setting a two-sided P value of 0.0498 for statistical significance in final analyses. To ensure at least 90% power, 691 events were required, assuming a true hazard ratio of 1.0. Noninferiority for the primary outcome was confirmed if the upper boundary of the two-sided 95.02% confidence interval was less than 1.3.

The primary analysis utilised a Cox proportional-hazards model adjusted for several baseline factors and geographic regions, with cumulative incidence functions corrected for death as a competing risk, except for all-cause mortality, which used Kaplan-Meier estimates. Cumulative incidence plots were truncated at 48 months due to declining patient numbers at risk. A modified intention-to-treat approach was adopted, including all patients who received at least one dose of the study drug, with data censored for patients without events on their last known event-free day. Secondary analyses compared the effects

of the 10 mg and 25 mg doses of empagliflozin against placebo. Repeated-measures analysis as a mixed model was used to evaluate changes in various clinical parameters from baseline, including glycosylated haemoglobin levels, weight, waist circumference, blood pressure, heart rate, and lipid levels[10].

3. Trial Emulation Study Design

3.1 Study population

In England, the NHS provides health care, free at the point of administration. We will use The National Diabetes Audit (NDA) to evaluate the cardiovascular disease outcomes of empagliflozin in individuals with type 2 diabetes with established cardiovascular disease. The NDA was established in 2003 and was developed to assess the quality of, and variation in, diabetes clinical care and outcomes across England for individuals with diabetes. From 2017, NDA data have been collected by the General Practice Extraction System, a national automated process that extracts data from primary care electronic patient records and from 2017/18 onwards, over 98% of general practices in England have provided data to the NDA. In addition, specialist secondary care health providers submit data extracts via a secure Clinical Audit Platform and from 2019/20 onwards, data on digital retinal screening have been submitted by the NHS Diabetes Eye screening programme. Data extracted include demographic data (e.g. age, sex, ethnicity, age at diagnosis, deprivation), clinical data (e.g. HbA1c measurements, blood pressure, cholesterol and body mass index) and from 2017/18, diabetes-related medication (glucose-lowering medications, antihypertensive medications and statins). Each audit period covers 15 months from 1 January in the first year to 31 March in the second year. The NDA will be linked by pseudo-NHS number to civil death registrations collated by the Office for National Statistics and hospital episode statistics (HES) which contains details about hospital admission, out-patient appointments, and attendance to Accident and Emergency departments (Figure 1)[12].

Figure1- Data flows for the National Diabetes Audit

3.2 Inclusion and Exclusion criteria

To ensure the target trial and the emulated trial using observational data are comparable, we need to establish a set of inclusion and exclusion criteria based on clinical expertise. This step is crucial for defining a consistent and relevant participant population, which minimises biases and enhances the validity of the comparisons.

Table 1 – Proposed Trial Emulation inclusion criteria using the NDA

Trial	Emulation
Age 18 or more at baseline	Individuals aged 18 years or older at the start of each audit period in which treatment starts, will be included.
Confirmed Type 2 diabetes	Individuals with type 2 diabetes are included in the NDA if they have a valid SNOMED code for type 2 diabetes in their electronic health record. Where there are inconsistencies in the type of diabetes recorded, the most recent type recorded by a specialist diabetes care provider will be used, if available. If the data have not been provided by a specialist diabetes provider, the most recent type of diabetes recorded in primary care will be used.
Body-mass index of 45 or less	Individuals with a BMI ≤ 45 kg/m² recorded within one year of start of treatment will be included. Individuals with a BMI < 12 kg/m ² will be assumed invalid. Individuals who do not have their BMI recorded will not be included.
No glucose-lowering agents for at least 12 weeks before randomisation and had a glycated haemoglobin level of at least 7.0% and no more than 9.0% or had received stable glucose-lowering therapy for at least 12 weeks before randomization and had a glycated haemoglobin level of at least 7.0% and no more than 10.0%.	Individuals whose latest HbA1c measurement, recorded within one year of start of treatment, and between 53 and 86 mmol/mol will be included
eGFR > 30 ml/min/173m ²	Individuals with an eGFR > 30 ml/min/173m ² recorded within two year of start of treatment. Individuals with an eGFR $> 1200?$ ml/min/173m ² will be assumed invalid. Individuals who do not have an eGFR value recorded will not be included.
<p>High risk of CVD event, having ≥ 1 of the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● History of myocardial infarction > 2 months prior to informed consent ● Evidence of multi-vessel coronary artery disease (i.e. 2 or more major coronary arteries or the left main coronary artery, documented by any of the following): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Presence of significant stenosis: $\geq 50\%$ luminal narrowing during angiography (coronary or multi-slice computed tomography) ○ Previous revascularization (percutaneous transluminal coronary angioplasty \pm stent or coronary artery bypass graft > 2 months prior to consent ○ The combination of revascularization in one major coronary artery and significant stenosis ($\geq 50\%$ luminal narrowing) in another major coronary artery ● Evidence of single-vessel coronary artery disease, $\geq 50\%$ luminal narrowing during angiography (coronary or multi-slice computed tomography) not subsequently successfully revascularized (with at least one of the following): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ A positive non-invasive stress test for ischemia 	At least one admission to hospital for heart failure, hypertension*, myocardial infarction, stroke, peripheral vascular disease or atrial fibrillation over the previous 10 years prior to start of treatment (ICD-10 codes in appendix)

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Hospital discharge for unstable angina ≤ 12 months prior to consent ● Unstable angina > 2 months prior to consent with evidence of single-or multi-vessel coronary artery disease ● History of stroke (ischemic or hemorrhagic) > 2 months prior to consent ● Occlusive peripheral artery disease documented by any of the following: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Limb angioplasty, stenting, or bypass surgery ○ Limb or foot amputation due to circulatory insufficiency ○ Evidence of significant peripheral artery stenosis ($> 50\%$ on angiography, or $> 50\%$ or hemodynamically significant via non-invasive methods) in 1 limb ○ Ankle brachial index < 0.9 in ≥ 1 ankle 	
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* Throughout the analysis, we define Hypertension as either having a record of Systolic blood pressure ≥ 140 and Diastolic blood pressure ≥ 90 , within one year before starting one of the treatments of interest or having been prescribed anti-hypertensive drug within 180 days before starting the treatment.

Table 2 – Trial Emulation exclusion criteria using the NDA

Exclusion criteria	Emulation
Uncontrolled hyperglycaemia with glucose > 240 mg/dL after an overnight fast during placebo run-in and confirmed by a second measurement (not on the same day).	Not able to measure
Indication of liver disease, defined by serum levels of alanine aminotransferase, aspartate aminotransferase, or alkaline phosphatase above 3 x upper limit of normal during screening or run-in phase.	Admission to hospital with Liver disease up to 10 years prior to start of treatment (ICD-10 codes in appendix, Table 4)
Planned cardiac surgery or angioplasty within 3 months	Not able to measure
Estimated glomerular filtration rate < 30 ml/min/1.73 m ² (according to the Modification of Diet in Renal Disease equation) at screening or during run-in phase	Individuals whose latest eGFR < 30 ml/min/1.73 m ² within two year of start of treatment were excluded from the analyses. Individuals with no eGFR measurement recorded within one year of start of treatment were also excluded.
Bariatric surgery within the past two years and other gastrointestinal surgeries that induce chronic malabsorption	Individuals with bariatric surgery recorded within the past 2 years prior to start of treatment, will be excluded (ICD-10 codes in appendix).
Blood dyscrasias or any disorders causing haemolysis or unstable red blood cells	Not able to measure
Medical history of cancer (except for basal cell carcinoma) and/or treatment for cancer within the last 5 years	Admissions to hospital with cancer recorded (in any position on the record) up to 5 years prior to start of treatment will be excluded (ICD-10 codes in appendix).
Contraindications to background therapy according to the local label	Not able to measure
Treatment with anti-obesity drugs 3 months prior to informed consent or any other treatment at time of screening leading to unstable body weight	Not able to measure
Treatment with systemic steroids at time of informed consent or change in dosage of thyroid hormones within 6 weeks prior to informed consent	Not able to measure
Any uncontrolled endocrine disorder except type 2 diabetes	Individuals with any admissions to hospital for uncontrolled endocrine disorder, except type 2 diabetes will be excluded (ICD-10 codes in appendix).
Pre-menopausal women (last menstruation ≤ 1 year prior to informed consent) who were nursing, pregnant, or of child-bearing potential and were not practising an acceptable method of birth control, or did not plan to continue using this method	Not able to measure

throughout the study, or did not agree to submit to periodic pregnancy testing during the trial <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Acceptable methods of birth control include tubal ligation, transdermal patch, intrauterine devices/systems, oral, implantable or injectable contraceptives, sexual abstinence, double barrier method, vasectomy of partner 	
Alcohol or drug abuse within 3 months of informed consent that would interfere with trial participation or any ongoing condition leading to decreased compliance with study procedures or study drug intake	Individuals with any admissions to hospital for alcohol or drug abuse 3 months prior to start of treatment will be excluded (ICD-10 codes in appendix).
Intake of an investigational drug in another trial within 30 days prior to intake of study medication in this trial or participating in another trial involving an investigational drug and/or follow-up	Not able to measure
Any clinical condition that would jeopardise patient safety while participating in this clinical	Not able to measure
Acute coronary syndrome, stroke, or transient ischemic attack within 2 months prior to informed consent	Any occurrence of the primary or secondary outcomes within 2 months prior to start of treatment
In South Africa: blood pressure >160/100 mmHg at screening	n/a

4. Study duration and follow-ups

The overall trial duration was determined by a specific number of outcome occurrences. The first SGLT2 pharmacotherapy was approved in the UK in 2014. Therefore, in the emulation, we will include the timeframe from Mid-2017 to 2020/21, ensuring a minimum of three years of follow-up.

The index date (time zero) is defined as the first instance when a patient redeems a prescription for one of the pharmacotherapies of interest and meets the inclusion and exclusion criteria within the specified time period. Follow up measurements if available, refer to measurements closest to the middle of the interval.

5. Treatment of interest

In the original trial, the comparator group was a placebo. The protocol justified the ethical acceptability of this design by incorporating appropriate criteria for patient discontinuation, the ability to adjust background treatment to meet glucose and HbA1c goals, and predefined criteria for rescue therapy in line with relevant guidelines. These measures ensured that patient safety was maintained despite the use of a placebo.

For the emulated trial using observational data, we will use a DPP-4 inhibitor as the active comparator instead of a placebo. This decision is based on the hypothesised neutral effects of DPP-4 inhibitors on cardiovascular outcomes, making them a suitable and ethical alternative to a placebo. By including DPP-4 inhibitors as the comparator, we aim to create a realistic and ethically sound emulation of the target trial, while still being able to evaluate the comparative effectiveness and safety of the treatment of interest against a relevant and commonly used alternative.

The aim of the trial emulation is to primarily compare continuous treatment with SGLT2 inhibitors against continuous treatment with DPP4 inhibitors over a period of 1-3 years. We will employ a discrete time scale with intervals of six months. In each six-month period, patients will be considered to be on treatment if they have redeemed at least one prescription within that interval. This approach allows for a practical and structured assessment of treatment adherence and effectiveness over time, ensuring that the comparison between SGLT2 and DPP4 inhibitors remains consistent and robust throughout the study period

5. Outcome(s)

In the EMPA-REG trial, the primary outcome was a composite of death from cardiovascular causes, nonfatal myocardial infarction (excluding silent myocardial infarction), or nonfatal stroke. The key secondary outcome was a composite of the primary outcome plus hospitalisation for unstable angina. For the target trial emulation, we will define the primary outcome as the first occurrence of cardiovascular death, nonfatal myocardial infarction, or nonfatal stroke. The secondary outcome will be the first occurrence of the primary outcomes or unstable angina.

6. Variable selection

Explicitly emulating a target trial alone cannot eliminate the bias that arises from the lack of randomization, such as confounding from non comparable treatment groups. Even if the observational analysis accurately emulates all other components of the target trial, confounding remains a significant challenge. To address this, successful target trial emulation requires detailed data not only on treatment and outcomes but also on potential confounders.

Some sources of routinely collected data, such as administrative claims databases, may provide reasonably detailed information on treatments and outcomes but often lack sufficient data on clinical factors that need adjustment. This limitation can hinder the ability to control for confounding effectively. The key advantage of a correct target trial emulation is that it eliminates other common sources of bias, allowing researchers to concentrate on addressing confounding. By ensuring detailed and comprehensive data collection on confounders, alongside treatments and outcomes, the emulation can more accurately approximate the conditions of a randomised trial, thus improving the validity of the causal inferences drawn from the observational study[4].

To select the proper variables for adjustment in our target trial emulation, we will use the disjunctive cause criterion[13]. This criterion posits that sufficient control for confounding can be achieved by choosing as confounders those variables that are causes of the exposure or outcome or both, then, additionally, discarding any variable known to be an instrumental variable, and including variables that do not satisfy the criterion but are good proxies for unmeasured common causes of the exposure and the outcome [13].

7. Potential confounders

We will consider two groups of variables: pre-treatment variables and time-varying variables. These variables will help control for confounding and ensure a robust comparison between continuous treatment with SGLT2 inhibitors and DPP4 inhibitors. Pre-treatment and baseline variables will be assessed at baseline or up to 10 years before baseline to control for confounding factors present before treatment initiation. Time-varying variables will be updated throughout the study period to account for changes that may affect treatment outcomes.

Table 3 - potential confounders

Pre-treatment and baseline variable	Time-varying variables
Age (continuous)	
Sex (male, female or unspecified)	
Index of multiple deprivation (calculated from each individuals postcode)	
Ethnicity	
Duration of diabetes (categorised as 0-5, 5-10, >10 years)	
HbA1c (continuous), recorded a maximum of 1 year before start of treatment	
Cholesterol (continuous): Due to missingness of the data, Cholesterol was not included as baseline	
Blood pressure (continuous): Due to missingness of the data, Blood pressure was not included as baseline	
Glomerular filtration rate based on creatinine (eGFR): Due to missingness of the data, eGFR was not included as baseline	
Concomitant glucose lowering treatment	Concomitant glucose lowering treatment
History of atrial fibrillation	
History of myocardial infarction	
History of heart failure	
History of stroke	
History of peripheral artery disease	
History of renal disease	
History of diabetic eye disease	
Therapy with: Aldosterone receptor antagonists Beta-blockers Angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors/angiotensin receptor-2 blockers Loop diuretics Calcium channel blockers Thiazide diuretics Statins	Therapy with: Aldosterone receptor antagonists Beta-blockers Angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors/angiotensin receptor-2 blockers Loop diuretics Calcium channel blockers Thiazide diuretics Statins

Concomitant Glucose-Lowering Treatment, & Therapy included as a baseline covariate by examining the treatment 180 days before baseline and as a time-varying confounder if initiated after baseline.

8. Data preparation:

We will explore the distribution of all continuous variables using relevant measures and graphs, such as measures of central tendency and variation, box plots, histograms, and Q-Q plots, to identify outliers. Any outliers found will be checked to determine if they are clinically plausible or if they are due to measurement error.

To address missing data, we will check the mechanism of missingness using formal tests like Little's MCAR test and graphical methods, such as heatmap plots. For data imputation, we will use random forest -based methods i.e. Multiple Imputation by Chained Equations Random Forest (MICE RF)[14],). Studies have shown that this method is suitable for complex epidemiological studies and can produce unbiased estimates of (log) hazard ratios. Parameter estimates are less biased using random forest MICE, and confidence interval coverage is improved [15].

9. Analysis

9.1 Target parameter of interest

Risk difference/ratio between taking SGLT2i for 1-3 years (unless otherwise clinically indicated) without the addition of DPP4i, compared to taking DPP4 for 1-3 years (unless otherwise clinically indicated) without the addition of SGLT2.

9.2 Descriptive analysis

Initially, we will calculate summary statistics for both continuous and categorical variables. Continuous variables will be described using measures of central tendency such as mean and median, and measures of dispersion like standard deviation and interquartile range. Categorical variables will be summarised with frequencies and percentages.

Baseline characteristics will be compared between treatment groups using appropriate statistical tests to assess the balance before treatment initiation. Additionally, we will provide a detailed summary of the use of SGLT2 inhibitors and DPP4 inhibitors, both as initial and time-varying treatments, and the incidence of primary and secondary outcomes across treatment groups. For time-varying variables, incidence rates over time will be calculated, and Kaplan-Meier curves will visualise time-to-event data for key outcomes. After performing multiple imputations, we will compare the distribution of imputed data with the original data to ensure that imputation has not introduced bias. These descriptive analyses will provide a solid foundation for the subsequent inferential analyses, ensuring that any findings are based on a thorough understanding of the data.

To capture changes in HbA1c levels over time, we will use longitudinal graphs. These graphs will display the trends in HbA1c for both medication groups, highlighting how glycaemic control evolves during the study period. By plotting individual patient trajectories as well as group averages, we can observe the overall effectiveness and variability of each treatment. Additionally, these graphs will help identify any significant shifts in HbA1c levels that may correspond with treatment adjustments or discontinuations.

Furthermore, we will analyse prescription patterns and treatment adherence using longitudinal data. Graphs will show the frequency of treatment dropouts and switches, providing insights into patient adherence and the sustainability of each treatment strategy. These visualisations will enable us to

identify common reasons for discontinuation and assess whether patients who switch treatments exhibit different clinical outcomes compared to those who remain on their initial medication.

9.3 Longitudinal Targeted Maximum Likelihood Estimation (LTMLE)

We will employ a discrete time scale with periods of six months ($t=0, 6, 12, \dots, 36$) to estimate the target parameters using a longitudinal targeted minimum loss estimator (LTMLE)(ref). LTMLE is a robust statistical method that accounts for time-varying covariates and treatments, providing accurate and unbiased causal effect estimates [16, 17].

Our data will be structured into 6-month intervals, creating a longitudinal dataset where each participant has multiple records corresponding to each 6-month period. Each record will include both time-varying covariates (e.g., HbA1c levels, incident health conditions, concomitant medications) and treatment status for that interval. Baseline covariates such as age, sex, and initial health conditions will be included as static variables.

LTMLE updates an initial sequential regression estimator using inverse probability weighting, accounting for the propensity of treatment and the probability of not being censored using Super Learner approach. SL is an ensemble method that allows researchers to combine several different prediction algorithms into one where the candidate algorithms can be quite different. It uses K-fold cross-validation to build the optimally weighted combination of predictions from a library of candidate machine learning algorithms [18, 19]. The estimation procedure involves several key steps:

Model Specification:

Define models for the treatment mechanism (the probability of receiving SGLT2 inhibitors versus DPP4 inhibitors given past covariates and treatment history) and the outcome mechanism (the probability of the outcome given past covariates and treatment history).

Initial Estimates:

Obtain initial estimates of the outcome and treatment probabilities using these models. All nuisance parameter regression models necessary for the initial estimator and for the targeting step will be adjusted for additive effects of all covariates updated to the current time interval, ensuring the causal time order of the variables is maintained.

Targeted Update:

Apply a targeting step to adjust the initial estimates using inverse probability weights. Specifically, we will regress the outcome, treatment, and censoring variables defined in the calendar time interval ($t, t+6$ months) on the most recent values of the time-dependent covariates at time t and the entire history of the treatment variables up to time t .

Penalised Ridge Regression:

Fit all nuisance parameter models using penalised ridge regression, selecting penalty parameters to under smooth the regression fits, which helps in reducing the bias in the estimates.

Iterative Process:

The targeting step is iterated until the estimates converge, ensuring the final estimates are consistent with the observed data and the specified causal model.

Reporting and Interpretation:

The primary analysis will focus on estimating the causal effect of continuous treatment with SGLT2 inhibitors compared to DPP4 inhibitors on the primary and secondary outcomes over the study period. We will report the longitudinal targeted minimum loss estimates (LTMLE) with 95% confidence intervals. These estimates will provide robust and interpretable causal insights into the comparative effectiveness of SGLT2 inhibitors and DPP4 inhibitors in real-world clinical practice.

By employing LTMLE, we address the complexities of time-varying treatments and covariates, ensuring that our analysis correctly models the dynamic nature of treatment effects and confounding factors over time. This approach will yield reliable and nuanced insights into the long-term impacts of these diabetes treatments.

9.4 Subgroup and sensitivity analysis

In line with the subgroup analysis conducted in the EMPA-REG trial and ensuring an adequate sample size, we will stratify our analysis of the primary and secondary outcomes across several key demographic and clinical subgroups. These subgroups include sex, age group, ethnicity, baseline HbA1c levels, duration of diabetes, and Index of multiple deprivation. By examining treatment effects within these subpopulations, we aim to identify potential variations in treatment response and assess the generalisability of our findings across diverse patient profiles.

When stratifying the data for the subgroup analysis, we will investigate the data for sparse data problem and amend the analysis accordingly.

As part of our sensitivity analysis, we will implement a grace period of 30 days by shifting the index date to day 30 after treatment initiation. This adjustment allows for a more flexible definition of treatment exposure, accounting for potential delays in treatment response or adherence variations during the initial phase of therapy. Following the adjustment, we will repeat our main analysis, including the estimation of primary and secondary outcomes, within this modified timeframe [20].

In addition, we will run the analysis using just one specific SGLT2i, Empagliflozin, as in the original trial, rather than using all SGLT2i, and estimate the risk difference between Empagliflozin and DPP4i.

By conducting sensitivity analyses, we can evaluate the robustness of our primary findings and assess the potential impact of methodological variations on our results. The inclusion of a grace period addresses potential misclassification of treatment exposure and ensures that our estimates remain valid under alternative modelling assumptions. Overall, these sensitivity analyses enhance the reliability and validity of our study findings, providing a comprehensive evaluation of the treatment effects observed in our primary analysis.

10. Appendix

Table 4- Secondary care data and mortality data available through linkage of the NDA

Medical Condition	ICD codes
Heart failure	I50.1, I50.20-23, I50.30-33, I50.40-43, I50.9
Myocardial infarction	I121.0-9, I122.0-9
Stroke	I61.0-9, I63.0-9, I166, I169
Peripheral artery disease	I170.20-29
Renal disease	N18.3-5, E10.2, E11.2
Diabetic eye disease	E11.319, 321.331, 341, 351, E11.321, 3211, 331, 3311, 341, 3411, 351, 3511, E11.39
Atrial Fibrillation	I48.0, 148.1, 148.11, I48.11, I48.19, I482, 21, 3, 4, 91, 92, I44.91, 92,
Hypertension	I10, I11, I11.0, 11.9
Cancer	C00-C14, C15-26, C30-39, C40-41, C43-58, C60-97
Liver disease	K70-77
Endocrine disorder except type 2 diabetes	E00-07, E15-16, E20-35
Alcohol or drug abuse	F10-19
Chronic Obstructive pulmonary disease	J40, J43, J44
Unstable Angina	I20.0-9, I24
Bariatric surgery	0DBM0ZZ
Revascularization	02703ZZ 02713ZZ, 02723ZZ 02733ZZ 02763ZZ 02773ZZ 02783ZZ 02793ZZ 02793ZZ
Mortality	R99
All-cause mortality	R99
Cardiovascular mortality	

Table 5- Glucose-lowering prescriptions available in NDA

Medication	ATC code*
Glucose-lowering prescriptions	
DDP-4 inhibitors	Z79.84
GLP-1 receptor agonists	Z79.84
Glucosidase inhibitors	Z79.84
Insulin	Z79.84
Meglitinides	Z79.84
Metformin	Z79.84
SGLT2 inhibitors	Z79.84
Sulfonylureas	Z79.84
Thiazolidinediones	Z79.84
Blood pressure lowering prescriptions	Z79.51 Z79.52 Z79.899 Z79.899 Z79.899
Aldosterone receptor antagonists	Z79.899
Beta-blockers	Z79.51
Angiotensin-converting enzyme inhibitors/angiotensin receptor-2 blockers	Z79.52
Loop diuretics	Z79.899
Calcium channel blockers,	Z79.899

Thiazide	Z79.899
Cholesterol-lowering prescriptions	Z79.02
Statins	Z79.02

*In NDA we will use SNOMED codes:

https://eur03.safelinks.protection.outlook.com/?url=https%3A%2F%2Fdigital.nhs.uk%2Fbinaries%2Fcontent%2Fassets%2Fwebsite-assets%2Fdata-and-information%2Fdata-collections%2Fqof%2Fbusiness-rules-2023-2024%2Fnda_v7.0.zip&data=05%7C02%7Csg18%40leicester.ac.uk%7C73f68d668bf94f47e7fe08dc96a4d837%7Caebecd6a31d44b0195ce8274afe853d9%7C0%7C1%7C638550881965779184%7CUnknown%7CTWFpbGZsb3d8eyJWljojMC4wLjAwMDAiLCJQIjoiV2luMzliLCJBTiI6IjEkaWwiLCJXVCi6Mn0%3D%7C0%7C%7C%7C&sdata=31BZpJPdraNvjV5w6QYo5egLXXFdWXLvJfgp7Gb3NOs%3D&reserved=0

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